

1 B cells silence EZH2 and activate EZH1 during lineage commitment from the HSC.

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We demonstrate here that B cells silence *EZH2* and activate *EZH1* during lineage commitment from the HSC.

7 Citations

8 1. Su, I.H., Basavaraj, A., Krutchinsky, A.N., Hobert, O., Ullrich, A., Chait, B.T. and Tarakhovsky, A.,
9 2003. Ezh2 controls B cell development through histone H3 methylation and Igh rearrangement. Nature
10 immunology, 4(2), pp.124-131.